

Design and Implementation of a Consensus-Driven Malware Analysis System using Deep Learning and Blockchain

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Abstract

The increasing sophistication of malware in distributed and adversarial environments highlights the urgent need for secure, scalable, and trustworthy detection mechanisms beyond traditional centralized solutions. This research proposes a consensus-driven malware analysis framework that integrates static malware feature extraction, deep learning-based classification, and blockchain-enabled consensus. The system employs static analysis to extract features for training a convolutional neural network (CNN), ensuring accurate malware detection. To avoid single points of failure, the trained model is deployed across multiple blockchain nodes performing parallel analysis. The Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance (PBFT) protocol is used to achieve consensus over node level predictions, thereby ensuring resilience against faulty or malicious participants. Smart contracts enforce immutable recordings of results and consensus rules, while a reputation-based trust mechanism dynamically updates node reliability. The final report is delivered transparently and remains auditable, demonstrating the effectiveness of consensus protocols in enhancing the reliability and robustness of decentralized malware analysis systems.

1 Introduction

Malware, short for "malicious software" is any program or code that disrupts, damages, or allows unauthorized access to computer systems, networks, or data. It has become a major challenge in the digital age. Unlike regular software designed to assist users, malware is created with harmful intentions. It often hides in files, emails, or websites, waiting to exploit system weaknesses. There are several types of malwares i.e. Viruses attach to files and spread when those files are shared. Worms replicate on their own across networks. Trojans masquerade as useful applications while secretly compromising systems. Spyware monitors user activity without consent. Ransomware locks important data until the victim pays a ransom. The effects of malware can be severe. It can slow down devices, corrupt or delete files, steal sensitive information like passwords or banking details, and even give attackers remote control over entire systems. Global smartphone shipments grew by 3.6quarter of 2024. Android holds over 70Smartphones and mobile apps have become essential in modern life, providing services such as online shopping, banking, social networking, and entertainment. As mobile technology advances, users rely more on their devices to store sensitive information, including personal details, financial records, and private messages. However, this convenience brings significant risks. The open-source nature of the Android operating system encourages innovation and flexibility but also makes it a target for malicious actors. With the increase in Android users worldwide, malware attacks on these devices have risen sharply. Malware can enter smartphones through seemingly

harmless apps by exploiting permissions and system vulnerabilities. It can steal data, disrupt services, or gain unauthorized access. Traditional antivirus solutions depend on signature updates, which often struggle to keep pace with evolving attack methods. This has created an urgent need for better detection systems that can respond to new threats in real time. Researchers are now using machine learning and deep learning techniques. These methods analyse large datasets of applications to uncover hidden patterns of malicious behaviour. Combined with blockchain technology for transparency and trust, these approaches provide a more secure framework for protecting mobile users against increasing cyberattacks. Malicious software targeting mobile devices, especially those on the Android platform, has become one of the biggest cybersecurity challenges in recent years. The open-source nature of Android and its widespread use make it a prime target for attackers. They exploit vulnerabilities to gain unauthorized access, steal sensitive information, or disrupt normal functions. As the number of Android users grows, the frequency and complexity of malware attacks have soared, posing serious risks to individuals and organizations. To address these challenges, researchers have proposed various deep learning-based solutions. These models use extensive datasets and advanced neural architectures to find hidden patterns that differentiate malicious applications from safe ones. While these techniques show promising results in detection accuracy, they often rely on complex architectures and intricate mechanisms. Although this complexity aids in capturing subtle features, it creates challenges related to efficiency, scalability, and resource use. In mobile settings with limited resources, balancing detection performance and cost is critical. As a result, current research is focused on lightweight yet effective models that deliver high accuracy without using too many resources. There is also interest in combining deep learning with decentralized technologies like blockchain to improve transparency, trust, and resilience. By merging smart detection with secure consensus methods, future systems aim to provide strong protection against evolving malware threats while remaining efficient and practical. For these reasons, it's important to understand malware and its various types. There are two primary approaches to malware analysis: static analysis and dynamic analysis. Static analysis looks at malware without running it, examining its code, file structure, and embedded strings. While this method is quick and safe, heavily obfuscated or encrypted malware can evade detection, leaving analysts with incomplete information. Dynamic analysis, however, involves running malware in a controlled environment like a sandbox to monitor its behaviour. This approach reveals real-time actions, such as file modifications, registry changes, or network communication. Nevertheless, if the malware detects the sandbox, it may change its behaviour, misleading analysts. By applying these methods, we can analyse malware before executing any file. This process is called malware analysis. We are working on a project called the Design and Implementation of a Consensus Driven Malware Analysis System using Deep Learning and Blockchain, which aims to tackle this problem using Static Analysis. Since the rapid growth of Android applications has been accompanied by a significant increase in the complexity and volume of malware, posing serious challenges to conventional centralized malware detection systems. Traditional approaches suffer from limitations such as single points of failure, lack of transparency, and vulnerability to manipulation in distributed environments [1]. To address these challenges, this work presents a consensus-driven decentralized malware analysis framework that integrates static analysis, deep learning, and blockchain technology. Static features extracted from Android applications are used to train deep learning-based classifiers for accurate malware detection, as supported by earlier studies [2]. To enhance reliability and trust, the trained model is deployed across multiple blockchain nodes that independently perform analysis. A Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance (PBFT) consensus protocol is employed to aggregate node-level predictions and ensure correct decision-making even in the presence of faulty or malicious nodes [3]. Blockchain-based smart contracts provide immutable storage, transparency, and auditability of analysis results, while a reputation-based trust mechanism evaluates node reliability over time. By combining deep learning-based detection with consensus-driven coordination, the proposed framework aims to deliver a secure, scalable, and trustworthy solution for decentralized Android malware analysis. This synopsis emphasizes the critical role of consensus protocols in enabling secure and reliable decentralized malware analysis systems. With the continuous evolution of Android malware, centralized detection frameworks face growing challenges related to trust, transparency, and fault tolerance [1]. Although static analysis and deep learning-based classifiers have demonstrated high detection accuracy, their deployment in distributed environments introduces new risks such as inconsistent predictions and compromised analysis nodes [2]. Consensus protocols address these challenges by enforcing strict decision rules that prevent any single node from influencing the final outcome. In particular, Byzantine fault-tolerant protocols such as PBFT provide deterministic agreement and

strong correctness guarantees, even when a subset of nodes behaves maliciously [3]. The integration of blockchain technology further enhances system reliability by ensuring transparent coordination, immutable record keeping, and auditability of security decisions [4]. Additionally, reputation-based trust mechanisms improve system robustness by dynamically evaluating node reliability over time. Overall, the reviewed concepts demonstrate that consensus protocols are not merely coordination tools but essential security components in decentralized malware analysis systems. Their integration with static analysis and deep learning-based detection provides a strong foundation for building secure, scalable, and trustworthy Android malware detection frameworks capable of operating effectively in adversarial environments.

2 Literature Review

The literature reviewed in this chapter highlights the continuous evolution of Android malware detection techniques in response to increasingly sophisticated cyber threats. Early approaches relied primarily on signature-based detection; however, these methods proved insufficient against polymorphic and obfuscated malware. Consequently, researchers shifted toward static, dynamic, and hybrid analysis techniques supported by machine learning and deep learning models. Among these, static analysis has emerged as a widely adopted approach due to its low computational overhead and effectiveness in extracting discriminative features such as permissions, API calls, opcode sequences, and control-flow patterns [1], [5], [17]. Numerous studies published in IEEE and ACM venues demonstrate that deep learning-based classifiers trained on static features can achieve high detection accuracy in controlled and centralized environments. Despite their effectiveness, centralized malware detection architectures suffer from inherent limitations. Several studies report that centralized systems are vulnerable to single points of failure, lack transparency, and depend heavily on trusted authorities for decision-making [8], [13]. These weaknesses become more pronounced in distributed and collaborative security settings, where multiple autonomous entities contribute analysis results. In such environments, the presence of compromised or malicious nodes can significantly degrade system reliability, leading to false reporting or manipulated detection outcomes. Foundational research on distributed systems provides critical insights into addressing these challenges. The Byzantine Generals Problem introduced by Lamport, Shostak, and Pease established the theoretical difficulty of achieving reliable agreement in systems with faulty or malicious participants [6]. Building on this work, Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance (PBFT) proposed by Castro and Liskov demonstrated that deterministic consensus is achievable when fewer than one-third of participating nodes are faulty, even under asynchronous network conditions [7]. These studies laid the groundwork for designing secure and fault-tolerant distributed decision-making systems, which are highly relevant to decentralized malware detection frameworks. Recent literature reflects a growing interest in applying consensus mechanisms to security analytics. Distributed malware analysis systems aim to improve scalability and fault tolerance by allowing multiple nodes to independently inspect applications. However, early decentralized approaches often relied on simplistic decision rules such as majority voting or assumed the existence of trusted coordinators, which exposed systems to collusion and insider attacks [8]. To overcome these limitations, researchers emphasize the need for robust consensus protocols capable of operating in adversarial environments. Blockchain technology has further accelerated research in consensus-driven security solutions. Nakamoto's work on blockchain demonstrated that decentralized consensus could be achieved without centralized control using cryptographic verification and incentive mechanisms [9]. Subsequent studies show that blockchain-based consensus enhances data integrity, transparency, and non-repudiation in distributed systems [10]. However, probabilistic consensus mechanisms such as Proof of Work and Proof of Stake may introduce latency and resource inefficiency, making them less suitable for time-sensitive malware detection tasks. In contrast, Byzantine fault-tolerant consensus protocols offer deterministic finality and stronger correctness guarantees, which are particularly advantageous for permissioned and security critical environments [11].

3 Methodology and Work Planning

The proposed work adopts a decentralized and consensus-driven methodology for Android malware detection by integrating static analysis, deep learning techniques, blockchain infrastructure, and the

Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance (PBFT) consensus protocol. The overall objective of the methodology is to enhance the reliability, transparency, and trustworthiness of malware detection decisions in distributed environments where individual analysis nodes may be faulty or compromised [2]. The methodology begins with dataset preparation using the publicly available Andro Zoo repository, which contains millions of Android applications collected from multiple sources such as Google Play and third-party markets [23]. For experimental feasibility, the large latest.csv file is reduced to a balanced subset of applications consisting of malicious samples with high Virus Total detection scores and benign samples with zero detection scores. This reduced dataset serves as the foundation for feature extraction and model training. Static analysis is employed to extract meaningful application-level features without executing the application. Using Virus Total reports, permission-based and service-based features are collected based on the SHA-256 hash values of the selected applications [24]. These features are stored in structured CSV files and represent the behavioural footprint of Android applications. Static analysis is chosen due to its efficiency, scalability, and suitability for large scale malware analysis environments [17]. After feature extraction, multiple deep learning models are evaluated to determine the most suitable classifier for malware detection. Models such as Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), Deep Neural Network (DNN), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks are trained and tested on both permission-based and service-based datasets. Performance evaluation is conducted using standard metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. The model demonstrating the highest detection accuracy is selected for deployment across the blockchain network [5]. To eliminate centralized decision making, the selected deep learning model is replicated across multiple blockchain nodes. Each node independently analysis the uploaded APK file and produces a malware probability score. These individual predictions are then aggregated using the PBFT consensus protocol, ensuring that no single node can influence the final decision [4]. A weighted aggregation mechanism is employed, where each node’s contribution is influenced by its trust value, thereby improving robustness against unreliable or malicious participants [18]. Blockchain technology is used to provide transparency, immutability, and auditability to the detection process. Ethereum-based smart contracts are implemented using the Solidity programming language to securely store detection results, enforce consensus rules, and prevent unauthorized modifications [26]. A reputation-based trust management mechanism dynamically updates the trust value of each node based on the deviation between its individual prediction and the final consensus result, strengthening long-term system reliability. For implementation and testing, the system is deployed on a simulated Ethereum environment using Ganache, which enables controlled experimentation with multiple blockchain nodes and accounts. All system events, including malware analysis results and trust updates, are recorded on the blockchain as immutable transactions, ensuring traceability and accountability. Overall, the proposed methodology systematically integrates static analysis, deep learning, and blockchain-enabled consensus to overcome the limitations of traditional centralized malware detection systems. The work plan follows a structured sequence of dataset preparation, feature extraction, model selection, decentralized deployment, consensus-based decision aggregation, and blockchain-backed validation, ensuring a secure, scalable, and trustworthy Android malware analysis framework.

4 IMPLEMENTATION

The proposed work starts by reducing the size of the Andro zoo dataset by forming two separate datasets, which are the permission-type dataset and the service-type dataset. This multi-process technique is explained in detail as follows. A. Reducing the size of latest.csv : Andrew Zoo has data about more than 21 lakh applications, and the size of the latest.csv file is more than 10 GB. The size of the dataset was reduced by choosing 746 entries with a VT detection value greater than 40 and 746 entries with a VT detection value of 0. The Python Dask library was used to increase the speed of execution. The resulting CSV file now has data about 1296 applications. This reduced dataset is taken as the base dataset, from which one dataset has application permission features, known as the permission-type dataset, and another dataset has data about network services, known as the services dataset. B. Creation of permission type dataset and services dataset: In order to fetch the permission and category details from VirusTotal, all the SHA-256 hash values from the newly created CSV file in step (A) were chosen and stored in a list. The SHA-256 hash values were then passed to VirusTotal for static analysis through a loop and the VirusTotal API key. However, VirusTotal allows only 500 requests per day, whereas analysis was needed for about 1296 applications. Hence, multiple API keys

Figure 1: Architecture of proposed system

were employed. After the request limit of one API key was exhausted, the next API key was employed to continue the process of fetching the analysis results for the remaining SHA-256 hash values. The results of VirusTotal were obtained in the form of key-value pairs in JSON format. VirusTotal’s static analysis yields details about all types of permissions used along with their respective counts. These details were fetched and stored in the CSV file of the permission-type data set. Similarly, details about services were fetched and stored in the service dataset CSV file. After that, the data is fed to the models for training and testing. The dataset is split into 70% training and 30% testing. Calculation of resultant probability in blockchain: Once the APK file is uploaded for analysis, each node runs its respective detection model and stores the probability value in the blockchain. The Ethereum smart contracts are implemented in the Ethereum Virtual machine (EVM) which gives them a secure and reliable environment to execute contracts that automatically enforce their logic. These contracts are important in supporting predetermined policies, including causing actions in reaction to the occurrence of particular events on the blockchain network. The contracts were written in Solidity programming language, which provides uniform and solid execution throughout the system. To implement and test the system, the system was implemented on a simulated blockchain environment using Ganache, an Ethereum development tool based on node.js. In Ganache, it is possible to create a local peer-to-peer blockchain network consisting of ten accounts that have been preconfigured, and each node in the network manages one account. The smart contracts collaborate using the accounts to evaluate the qualities of a given file. All the events and activities involved in the network including downloading of external files, updating of trust values and any other activities are subjected to hashing mechanism and are stored in the blockchain as transactions, which are usually known as ledgers. The overall system is made transparent and reliable through the overall record keeping procedure.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental evaluation of the proposed decentralized malware detection framework was conducted using a representative subset of the Andro Zoo dataset. Since the complete dataset contains more than five million Android applications and exceeds practical computational limits, a manageable subset was selected for systematic experimentation. A total of 1296 Android application packages (APKs) were used, consisting of 746 malicious samples with Virus Total detection scores greater than 40 and 550 benign samples with detection scores equal to zero. This sampling strategy ensures clear

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≡ DATASET_SUMMARY_report.txt X
D: > M_A > malware apk > ≡ DATASET_SUMMARY_report.txt
1 Dataset Summary Report
2 =====
3 Total Samples: 1296
4 Malware Samples: 746
5 Benign Samples: 550
6 Malware Percentage: 57.56%
7 Benign Percentage: 42.44%
8 Detected Label Column: LABEL
9 Dataset successfully used for training and testing.
10
11 End of Report
12
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Figure 2: Summary report of dataset

class separation and improves the reliability of model training and evaluation, as recommended in prior malware detection studies [10], [23]. Multiple deep learning architectures, including CNN, DNN, MLP, and LSTM, were trained and evaluated using permission-based and service-based static analysis features. The datasets were divided into training and testing subsets using a 70:30 split, and cross-validation was employed to reduce overfitting and enhance generalization [10]. The evaluation metrics considered include accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, which are widely used to assess classification performance in malware detection research [16], [17]. The results indicate that deep learning models are capable of effectively learning discriminative patterns from static Android application features. Permission-based attributes capture sensitive access behaviour, while service-based attributes provide additional contextual information related to application functionality. These observations are consistent with earlier studies that emphasize the effectiveness of static feature representation for Android malware detection [21], [27]. Overall, the models demonstrated balanced performance, showing that deep learning based classifiers are suitable for detecting malicious applications in static analysis settings. Beyond detection accuracy, the proposed system emphasizes reliability and trust through decentralized decision-making. Each blockchain node independently analysis the APK and generates a probability score indicating the likelihood of malicious behaviour. These individual predictions are aggregated using a consensus-based mechanism, ensuring that no single node can dominate the final decision. This approach significantly improves robustness against faulty or compromised nodes, aligning with prior research on Byzantine fault-tolerant security systems [4], [11]. From a system usability perspective, users are provided with flexible options to analyse APKs either by uploading the application file or by submitting its SHA-256 hash value. The final malware probability is displayed in percentage form, enabling intuitive interpretation of results. Blockchain-based smart contracts ensure that all analysis outcomes and trust updates are immutably recorded, providing transparency, traceability, and protection against unauthorized modification [3], [18]. Overall, the experimental observations confirm that integrating static analysis, deep learning models, and blockchain-enabled consensus mechanisms results in a secure, reliable, and scalable malware detection framework. The use of a representative dataset subset ensures experimental feasibility without compromising result validity, while the decentralized architecture effectively addresses the limitations of traditional centralized malware detection systems.

6 Conclusion

The primary cause for these problems is partly attributed to the proprietary nature of the Android architecture, coupled with its massive popularity among mobile device users. This increasingly emerging security threat is merely the tip of the iceberg, as there is immense scope for improvement in this area. We have clearly shown that hidden malware can be easily embedded within the package files of Android applications. It has been found that Android device security can be improved by using the Android blockchain for decentralized malware detection, which is a new and unprecedented method of improvement. There are also several areas where future research and development in this area can be explored. The growth of Android devices and applications has great potential, but it also brings challenges. This problem appears when trying to use a decentralized detection system that can scale

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